

TC FOR BE

TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE
FOR BIODIVERSITY & EQUITY

Grant agreement number: 101082057

TC4BE DELIVERABLE D2.2

Fostering Dialogue on Sustainable Cocoa Value Chains in Cameroon using the CamPod cocoa value chain strategy game

(M18, R, PU)

Lead party for deliverable: WU – Wageningen University
Document type: R
Due date of deliverable:
Actual submission date: 01-07-2025
Version: 1.0
Dissemination level: Public
Authors: Céline Dillman (LEAF), Marina Benitez Kanter (WUR), Marieke Sassen (WUR), Verina Ingram (WUR)
Reviewers: Verina Ingram (WU)

WP	Task	Deliverable	Authors (lead and others)	Participant organisation	Dissemination level	Report Date & Version	Deliverable Delivery date (month)
2	2.2	2.2	C. Dillman, M. Benitez Kanter, M. Sassen, V. Ingram	WU	PU	VI	01.07.2025

Partners

).

LEGAL NOTICE

The information in this document is provided as is and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

© LEAF and TC4BE, 2025. *Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.*

Citation: *Céline Dillman, Marina Benitez Kanter, Marieke Sassen, Verina Ingram. 2025. Fostering Dialogue on Sustainable Cocoa Value Chains in Cameroon using the CampPod cocoa value chain strategy game. TC4BE Deliverable 2.2. Wageningen University & Research. Wageningen 10.5281/zenodo.18337860*

DISCLAIMER

TCforBE is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA) and can not be held responsible for them. The Transformative Change for Biodiversity & Equity Project (TC4BE) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101082057.

These activities were also funded through the UK Research and Innovation's Global Challenges Research Fund under the Trade, Development, and the Environment Hub project (ES/S008160/1) and in-kind support from LEAF and the Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH-HAFL).

The Cocoa Change game is co-owned by Wageningen UR and LEAF.

This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101082057.

Contents

Abstract	4
1. TC4BE Background	4
TCforBE Project Summary	4
TCforBE aims and objectives.....	5
TCforBE overall approach.....	7
Glossary	8
2. Context Cameroon to Europe cocoa value chain	9
3. Developing the CAMPOD cocoa value chain game	10
4. Facilitation Training - Becoming a CamPod strategy game facilitator	10
Participants' Feedback and Learnings.....	11
Next steps	12
5. Using the game to inspire dialogue about sustainability in the value chain	12
Transferring Facilitation Capacities & Learnings from a facilitation perspective	12
Engagement and Empathy building.....	12
Shared Insights and a Vision for Change	13
Looking Beyond the Farm to the landscape	13
6. Conclusions and Next Steps.....	14

Abstract

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022 – 2026), supports transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It engages diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes. Work package (WP) 2 of the project specifically focuses on the governance pathways that can initiate transformative change from consumer countries, in particular the European Union.

As part of deliverable 2.2 of TCforBE we are analysing trade strategies to inform the development of transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity. This report details the development of a serious game to provide a case of the levers for change on biodiversity and equity and conditions for success in the cocoa sector originating from Cameroon. Defined as “games for research and not for leisure”, serious games use game theory and competitive resource allocation theories to explore the behaviour of systems, devise strategies and assess their strengths, and to support negotiations for collective and coordinated action. Numerous initiatives have been implemented to address the negative socio-environmental impacts of the cocoa value chain—such as laws, policies, regulations, market mechanisms (certifications and labelling), and social movements. The CamPod strategy game was developed by LEAF Inspiring Change, in collaboration with Wageningen University (WUR), Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH) and stakeholders from the cocoa sector in Cameroon. The game was designed to explore the dynamics between actors in the cocoa value chain and to better understand the economic, social and ecological impacts of different policy scenarios. The training and testing proved the CAMPOD Game to be a powerful tool for mobilising a diverse range of actors and encouraging inclusive and participatory dialogue on sustainability issues in the cocoa sector. By simulating realistic challenges and trade-offs, it fosters a deeper understanding of different perspectives and enables the collective exploration of ideas and strategies to enhance the resilience of the value chain.

This Game is part of the participatory research methods employed to incorporate diverse values and perspectives from stakeholders on various contested topics such as land use change, biodiversity loss, and poverty. An advantage of such methods is that they consider the positionality of stakeholders and the power dynamics between them. We recognize that knowledge inequities exist and reinforce negative power dynamics. By engaging with stakeholders and co-designing solutions, while facilitating knowledge exchange between groups like farmers and policymakers through unconventional and less confrontational methods (such as games), we aim to foster more equitable and systematic knowledge sharing, enabling diverse voices to be heard and driving transformative change. Using the CAMPOD Cocoa value Chain Game we will analyze the impacts that diverse existing and future initiatives on biodiversity and equity might have among the value chain, and particularly for producers and producing landscapes. Further games are planned in Europe and in Cameroon. The CAMPOD Game aids subsequent tasks of WP6 to contribute to envisioning an EU consumer country perspective and producing countries (WP4, WP5) perspectives on transformative change of food systems towards biodiversity and equity.

1. TC4BE Background

TCforBE Project Summary

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly ‘telecoupled’¹, i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU’s global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food

system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Underpinned by multi-stakeholder social learning cycles and attention to plural values, the researchers will seek to co-generate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU scales. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts. Envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities (e.g. rural imaginaries research, Bayesian tool development, case studies of corporate and regenerative enterprises). Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts).
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.

TCforBE aims and objectives

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and on how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support **transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems**. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

The project aims to inform policy discourse, e.g. the EU's Green Deal implementation, and especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aims to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and its climate resilience, and specifically responds to expert scientific advice that highlights a particular need for more social science evidence on **how to achieve a sustainable food system**. The project will generate such evidence, as well as contributions from and to environmental science on biodiversity measurement and valuation.

The project will also engage national policymakers and seek to inform landscape stewardship strategies in study landscapes in Africa and Latin America.

TCforBE contributes to four HORIZON EUROPE specific outcomes: 1) Sustainable pathways, 2) human dimensions, 3) social norms, behaviours, values, and 4) inform/motivate transformational change. The project work packages (WPs) address all the outcomes in a cross-cutting way and are arranged according to *scale of interest* (e.g. EU and global, national producer countries, landscape levels).

There are seven **work packages** addressing the project's specific objectives (Box 1), each with associated results and deliverables:

- WP 1 will generate insights on EU policies and societal shifts under new green policies in relation to food systems and modelling of potential impacts on relevant biomes.
- WP 2 explores transformative governance arrangements and levers for change. This includes analysis of trade and legal levers, social movements and collective action, and biodiversity governance initiatives, as well as identifying the best ways to engage with EU and other scale learning and communications stakeholders.
- WP 3 will summarise the taxonomy and related regulations targeting and enabling Biodiversity measurement and develop sustainable finance pathways that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics.
- WP 4 – national scale engagement and research – identification of current visions of future relating to food and territories (Q methodology), followed by social processes and researcher-led activities to co-frame and co-learn on transformative change pathways including generation of scenarios, geospatial mapping of commodity and policy impacts.
- WP 5 – landscape scale engagement and research - activities as in WP4, but the transformative change pathways will include generation of a Bayesian tool drawing on Q methodology and social learning, corporate/regen case studies, rural imaginaries (political ecology and ethnography).
- WP 6 will involve a conceptual framing, but also synthesis of findings and support for inter-landscape and global / EU dialogues on transformative change pathways.
- WP7 concerns management, dissemination and communication of the project.

Box 1: TCforBE Specific Objectives

Objective 1: Deepen understanding and capacity of agrifood policymakers on transformative pathways for biodiversity and equity in EU telecoupled agrifood systems,.

Objective 2: Identify, assess, and engage EU policymakers and stakeholders on demand-side consumer country governance arrangements for transformative change in telecoupled EU agrifood systems for positive biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Objective 3: Analyse and assess the potentials and limitations of existing biodiversity metrics, measurements, and finance levers (EU Action 68) and derive innovative financial instruments to achieve high biodiversity business transformations that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics (EU Actions 72 and 73).

Objective 4: Identify, co-analyse, and assess, with policymakers and stakeholders, national supply side producer country policies, scenarios and transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

Objective 5: To co-generate transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative landscapes, with high biodiversity and equity outcomes, drawing on new evidence and tools on biodiversity imaginaries, commodity impacts, SLI effectiveness/impacts, and corporate/regenerative enterprise.

Objective 6: Synthesise evidence and build global, regional and landscape learning to foster transformative change on biodiversity

All work packages will engage with communications, WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agrifood system stakeholders.

TCforBE overall approach.

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

The envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low- and middle-income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

Table 1 The Study Producer Countries and Landscapes

Country	Landscapes	Landscape characteristics
Cameroon	Dja-Tridom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emerging cocoa agrofood systems export timber and non-timber forest products (NTFP) trade, mining Medium-high levels of telecoupling Sustainability landscape initiatives (SLI) e.g. Dja Green cocoa landscape Large areas of rapidly degrading high-biodiversity forests, increasing agriculture
Colombia	Eastern Plains Llanos Orientales Magdalena River Cauca River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agricultural expansion for palm oil, cattle ranching, and reforestation programs. Megadiverse landscapes 20% in conservation and 30% in communal lands but facing violence, illicit economies, and weak state presence. Appropriation of public lands, encroachment into natural parks, local elites driving deforestation, displacement of smallholders
Kenya	Mau forest – Masai - Mara river basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wetlands - expanding rice production and fish farming, and grasslands with grazing systems High biodiversity forests, conservation areas Tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP-horticulture systems Medium levels of telecoupling Large areas of high biodiversity forest ecosystems & extensive agriculture Regenerative change & SLIs: MaMaSe program
	Mt Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grasslands (grazing systems) and tea-fruit-livestock-timber-horticulture systems High biodiversity forests, conservation areas Large areas high biodiversity forests, protected areas & extensive agriculture Medium-high levels of telecoupling SLIs: Mt Kenya Forest Landscape Restoration

Glossary

See [TC4BE glossary](#) for key terms and definitions

2. Context Cameroon to Europe cocoa value chain

The Cameroonian cocoa industry is embedded within a value chain marked by a significant and growing concentration of corporate power in trading, processing, and manufacturing. This concentration leads to adverse social and environmental effects such as violations of human and labor rights, low farmer incomes, and poverty (Squicciarini & Swinnen, 2016). The industry's power dynamics also contribute to environmental degradation, dependence on global markets, and the weakening of democratic structures (Ingram et al., 2018; Busquet et al., 2021; Waarts & Kiewisch, 2021).

Despite the numerous initiatives implemented to address the negative socio-environmental impacts of the cocoa value chain—such as laws, policies, regulations, market mechanisms (certifications and labelling), and social movements—there is a need to analyze which of these mechanisms, or a combination of them, might yield more positive biodiversity and equity outcomes along the value chain.

In a context where the institutional and legal context for the exportation of cocoa to the consumer markets is changing, with the introduction of the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR- [Regulation on Deforestation-free products - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/e300042c-325c-47e7-992d-e60118184000/asset/document/EUDR_Regulation_on_Deforestation-free_products_-_European_Commission_(europa.eu).pdf)) and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence (CSDD- [Corporate sustainability due diligence - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/e300042c-325c-47e7-992d-e60118184000/asset/document/CSDD_Corporate_sustainability_due_diligence_-_European_Commission_(europa.eu).pdf)), we analyse the impacts that these and other initiatives might have on the producing landscapes in Cameroon.

Defined as “games for research and not for leisure”, serious games use game theory and competitive resource allocation theories to explore the behaviour of systems, devise strategies and assess their strengths, and to support negotiations for collective and coordinated action (Speelman et al., 2017).

Participatory research methods have previously been employed to incorporate diverse values and perspectives from stakeholders on various contested topics such as land use change, biodiversity loss, and poverty (Van Noordwijk et al., 2023). One of the major advantages of these methods is that they consider the positionality of stakeholders and the power dynamics between them. We recognize that knowledge inequities exist and reinforce negative power dynamics. By engaging with stakeholders and co-designing solutions, while facilitating knowledge exchange between groups like farmers and policymakers through unconventional and less confrontational methods (such as art and games), we aim to foster more equitable and systematic knowledge sharing, enabling diverse voices to be heard and driving transformative change.

The **CAMPOD Cocoa Value chain Game** aims to analyze the impacts that diverse existing and future initiatives on biodiversity and equity might have among the value chain, and particularly for producers and producing landscapes.

The Cocoa Value chain Game is set up to be implemented with diverse stakeholders (Producers, Intermediaries, Governments, NGOs, social movements) among cocoa value chain in producing (Cameroon) and consuming countries (EU).

The results enable us to identify and compare the most effective interventions for promoting biodiversity and equity in the cocoa value chain. Additionally, through the game and subsequent discussions with participants, we aim to uncover the challenges and opportunities associated with each intervention. We will also identify common values, perceptions, and motivations that can inform the design and implementation of more sustainable value chains.

3. Developing the CAMPOD cocoa value chain game

In June 2025, LEAF Inspiring Change, in collaboration with Wageningen University & Research, conducted a training of trainers, followed by a series of interactive workshops with stakeholders from the cocoa value chain in Cameroon. The training of facilitators and the workshop series were part of the [TradeHub](#) project and the [TC4BE](#) project by Wageningen University & Research (WUR). The activities brought together more than 40 participants, including cocoa farmers, cooperative leaders, intermediaries, local NGOs, international organisations, academics, national and local government and traditional authorities. The goal was to explore the complex dynamics of the cocoa value chain through the innovative CamPod Cocoa Strategy Game.

The **CamPod strategy game** has been developed by LEAF Inspiring Change, in collaboration with Wageningen University (WUR), Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH) and stakeholders from the cocoa sector in Cameroon. The game was designed to explore the dynamics between actors in the cocoa value chain and to better understand the economic, social and ecological impacts of different policy scenarios. It is a powerful tool for mobilising a diverse range of actors and encouraging inclusive and participatory dialogue on sustainability issues in the cocoa sector. By simulating realistic challenges and trade-offs, it fosters a deeper understanding of different perspectives and enables the collective exploration of ideas and strategies to enhance the resilience of the value chain. Previously, the game has been played with cocoa sector experts in Côte d'Ivoire and stakeholders in the Netherlands.

4. Facilitation Training - Becoming a CamPod strategy game facilitator

The facilitation training, hosted by WUR and CIFOR-ICRAF in June 2025, brought together 15 participants in the CIFOR-ICRAF Central Africa regional office in Yaounde, Cameroon, who were interested in learning how to use the CamPod game in their own contexts. Over three days, the training guided participants through the game as both players and facilitators.

Playing the CamPod Game © M. Benitez

Switching roles – participants facilitating the game © M. Benitez

On the first day, participants immersed themselves in the game as players, discovering its structure, rules, and the systemic issues it models. They explored the setup, key mechanisms, and how different scenarios generate real-world dynamics relevant to cocoa value chains.

The second day focused on facilitation. Through interactive sessions, participants explored the posture of a good facilitator, effective facilitation techniques, and learnt how to guide game play and manage group dynamics. The afternoon was dedicated to practice, where participants took turns facilitating the game and received feedback from peers and trainers. Testing a jointly

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

developed new scenario, the practice also allowed the participants to deepen their understanding of how the game can effectively support real-world discussions.

Day three centred on debriefing and real-world applications. Participants learned how to structure post-game discussions to elicit systemic insights, encourage reflection, and connect gameplay to action. They also explored potential contexts for using CamPod. The training concluded with personal reflections and next steps for using the game in their work.

Participants' Feedback and Learnings

Participants expressed a strong appreciation for the realism and relevance of the CamPod game in capturing the complexities of the cocoa value chain. Many highlighted the game's ability to simulate real-world dynamics, provoke critical thinking, and facilitate meaningful dialogue among stakeholders. The approach was seen as not only insightful but also engaging, with several noting how it can uncover unexpected realities and support collective decision-making. Some participants shared striking realisations about their roles, strategies, and relationships within value chains.

"There's a close link between the game and reality. [And it helped me (better) understand my position in the value chain in relation to the other actors.] I realized that I have to elaborate a strategy as an actor. [I already started yesterday evening...]"

The facilitation component was particularly eye-opening for many. Participants appreciated learning about the posture and responsibilities of a facilitator and discovering new facilitation techniques. For some, this triggered reflections on their facilitation styles and the role of posture and neutrality.

Looking ahead, participants are eager to utilize the game in various settings, including technical committees, research protocols, environmental problem-solving, and capacity-building workshops. Several intend to test the game in upcoming projects, while others expressed interest in designing similar tools for different domains.

"I hope to use the game to facilitate discussions within the Sustainable Cocoa Committee at ONCC."

Despite the enthusiasm, some concerns remain. These include mastering the game's complexity, facilitating effective collaboration in real-world group settings, managing time efficiently, and ensuring inclusive participation. Participants also reflected on the potential relevance of adapting the game to include more value chain actors.

Above all, the training fostered a sense of ownership, motivation and collaboration. Many appreciated the group dynamics, the inclusive and supportive learning environment, and the facilitation style that encouraged openness and participation.

"In just 3 days, my perception relating towards all at stake has been reoriented."

"What I liked was the friendly atmosphere during the training. I'm the youngest here, but I didn't feel that way."

Figure 2 Evaluation of the training in terms of content and facilitation © LEAF

¹ All quotes in this report are translated versions of the French original quotes to facilitate legibility.

Next steps

Participants received a certificate of participation upon completing the training. A copy of the CamPod game is available at the CIFOR-ICRAF office in Yaoundé. Participants are encouraged to utilise the game in their own projects and to actively contribute to a growing community of practice by sharing their experiences and insights.

5. Using the game to inspire dialogue about sustainability in the value chain

As part of the TC4BE project, Wageningen University & Research organised three interactive workshops in Cameroon – one in Yaoundé and two in Lomié. These workshops brought together more than 35 participants, including cocoa producers -some of whom have an indigenous background-, members and leaders of cocoa cooperatives, cocoa traders, local and international organisations, national and local governments, and traditional authorities. The workshops aimed to immerse participants in the trade-offs faced by different actors in the cocoa value chain, balancing economic pressure, social inequalities, and ecological concerns, while deepening their understanding of how policies and market forces shape livelihoods and landscapes. In the discussion that followed the CamPod gameplay, reflections centred around future visions to transform the cocoa value chain for more positive biodiversity and equity.

Producers negotiating with the cooperative © LEAF

Producers discussing collective strategies © LEAF

Transferring Facilitation Capacities & Learnings from a facilitation perspective

LEAF co-designed and co-facilitated the workshops alongside researchers from WUR and the University of Dschang. Building on the previous facilitation training, two trainees supported the facilitation in Yaoundé and took the lead in Lomié, under the guidance of the LEAF facilitator. This “learning-by-doing” setup proved highly effective, offering continuous feedback while maintaining the quality of facilitation. Notably, two weeks after the workshops, the trainees independently facilitated a CamPod session with the staff of the University of Dschang.

From a facilitation standpoint, this setup generated valuable insights and highlighted what new facilitators find most challenging, as well as how different aspects of game facilitation impact group dynamics. One element that stood out was the critical role of storytelling. Using strong narratives that help participants imagine and situate themselves more effectively in the context, telling the story rather than mechanically reciting rules is a valuable skill to develop. Future facilitation training will incorporate these insights to enhance effectiveness.

Engagement and Empathy building

It was striking how effectively the game engaged participants. Many noted that the format, which initially seemed simple or playful, quickly became a powerful educational tool. The game broke down barriers, inviting all voices to contribute and fostering a lively, inclusive atmosphere – a stark contrast to other settings where engagement can be minimal. As one participant said,

In our country, games are for children. But this game broke down barriers

Another observed:

The approach was tailored to adults, with everyone participating - no one could fall asleep!

The illustrative design, objects, and role-play made complex supply chain dynamics accessible, as noted by participants in the rural area in particular.

Through the process, participants deepened their understanding of the cocoa value chain's multiple layers — from farm-level realities to international market demands, particularly the European Union's high standards. Many acknowledged that before the workshop, they had an incomplete picture of the value chain. The game clarified the importance of cooperatives, the challenges posed by intermediaries (coxeurs), and the pressures producers face.

I didn't know the whole value chain, now I understand it a little better."

Changing perspectives emerged as one of the most transformative aspects. Stepping into someone else's shoes allowed participants to expand their understanding of their own role relative to others. One cocoa producer who had vocally criticized the coxeurs found himself assigned to play one. His reaction?

"My ingenuity playing the role of the coxeur (intermediary/trader) surprised me."

Shared Insights and a Vision for Change

A recurring theme was the critical role of both collective and individual actions, aimed at adopting more sustainable production practices. These include a shift toward agroforestry systems and the reduction of pesticide use, reflecting growing concern about environmental and health impacts. Many participants recognised the need to strengthen cooperatives and avoid selling individually through co-ops, who often undermine producers' earnings. Group sales and better organisation within cooperatives were seen as vital steps toward obtaining fairer prices and greater market influence.

"We must help each other so that no one is left behind. It's important to sell as a group, because selling alone means losing."

Moreover, strengthening knowledge-sharing was also identified as a key step to empower producers. Regarding this aspect, the workshops inspired participants to become agents of change within their communities. Many expressed intentions to share what they had learned, whether through sensitising other producers about some of the challenges regarding biodiversity conservation and social equity, documenting farm activities to improve traceability, or the increasing need to experimenting the diversification of cocoa production, either transforming cocoa to other products like cocoa butter and powder, to add value locally; or looking for other alternative markets for other products such as avocados, bananas, honey, and handicrafts, that are also produced in the cocoa fields, and that could help to increase revenues at the household level.

Participants, particularly in Yaoundé, also recognised the need for improved financial literacy and planning. The experience of documenting sales and revenues in the game has demonstrated to some participants the value of regular monitoring for improved financial planning and decision-making. Others realised how crucial good planning is, and that failing to plan the season can be detrimental. They also observed the benefits of diversification and improved management strategies, such as better management of old plantations, intercropping with fruit trees, and integrating other revenue-generating activities.

Looking Beyond the Farm to the landscape

Discussions revealed a range of strategies across governance levels to promote sustainability in the cocoa sector. While much attention was centred on local actions and strategies with farmers, to foster the adoption of cocoa sustainable practices, several participants demonstrated a strong awareness of broader economic, social, and environmental systems. Notably, there was expressed

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

interest in a more active engagement of the private sector, the national and local governments, and international donors to advocate for improved regulation and greater support for sustainability goals.

At the market level, the diversification of marketing strategies emerged as essential. Participants highlighted the need to identify alternative markets for complementary products cultivated within cocoa landscapes—such as avocados, bananas, and other fruits—as a way to stabilise income and reduce dependence on cocoa alone.

At the national level, improving direct trade relationships between producers and intermediaries was seen as vital. Participants also called for efforts to expand domestic and regional markets, including the Cameroonian and broader African markets, to foster local cocoa consumption, and reduce reliance on volatile international demand.

At the institutional and policy level, a transition to more sustainable cocoa systems requires coordinated support across governance scales. The private sector was seen as a key actor in promoting landscape-level approaches that ensure fair pricing and enhance farmer well-being. Public institutions at local, regional, and national levels were called upon to invest in enabling infrastructure, such as roads, water access, and technical assistance.

Public-private partnerships were identified as essential vehicles for delivering capacity-building programs to improve sustainability practices. NGOs also have a crucial role in helping producers comply with evolving international standards, particularly EU requirements related to traceability and deforestation-free production.

Ultimately, achieving a more sustainable and inclusive cocoa value chain will depend on strengthened collaboration between actors at all levels—local, regional, national, and international. The participants shared concrete actions they plan to pursue, including cooperative development, knowledge exchange, policy advocacy, and the formation of new partnerships to scale up impact.

One participant reflected:

“We, as growers and cooperatives, must reach out to donors to ask for support... while recognizing that we also have an important role to play in collective success.”

6. Conclusions and Next Steps

The workshops successfully demonstrated the power of a participatory, game-based approach in connecting diverse stakeholders and generating meaningful dialogue around sustainability and equity in the cocoa value chain. The game’s ability to translate complex issues into shared experiences created a foundation for mutual understanding and collaborative problem-solving.

“I saw how some producers were unable to sell their cocoa – so we have to adapt to market demands, but also make it clear that we want to benefit from our work.”

Most importantly, participants affirmed that the game accurately reflects the realities they face in the cocoa value chain in Cameroon. This validation strengthens the tool’s credibility and allows us to use the game to tell the story outside of the Cameroonian context. It creates an opportunity to bridge the worlds between the local realities in production countries and the often detached perspectives in consumer countries of how cocoa is produced in the socioeconomic and environmental settings.

Producers negotiating with the coxeur © LEAF

Quote from the debriefing © LEAF

We also acknowledge the limitations of the strategy game approach. In all three workshops, it became apparent that future visioning is a rather unusual activity. Participants tended to remain anchored in their current realities and found it challenging to envision other solutions from what they know. For example, stopping the production and sale of cocoa was not an option chosen. Moreover, alternatives for overcoming deforestation and child labour, two of the major biodiversity and equity concerns, need to be explored further with complementary methods such as interviews, participant observation, attendance to congress and forums, etc. Finally, some ongoing issues regarding biodiversity conservation and sustainable livelihoods in Cameroon, and particularly in Dja Rainforest Complex, such as logging concessions and hunting, were not addressed during the workshops. From a facilitation perspective, we recognise the limitations of a one-day workshop and the need for long-term engagement, especially with members of local communities.

Moving forward, the CamPod game will be utilised in a similar format by WUR within the TC4BE project, engaging stakeholders in Europe, particularly those from the transformation sector and consumers. We plan to follow up with participants three months after the game session (early September 2025) to evaluate the impact of the experience further.

Contact details

Further Information and support in Cameroon: Verina Ingram verina.ingram@wur.nl or Jacques Bessengue at CIFOR-ICRAF j.bessengue@CIFOR-ICRAF.org

Further information about the TC4BE project: Marina Benitez-Kanter marina.benitezkanter@wur.nl or Verina Ingram verina.ingram@wur.nl

General information about the CamPod game and potential application in other contexts: hello@leafic.ch

